

FGMs INTERLAYERS IN DIFFUSION BONDING JOINTS

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SUMMARY: The paper presents basic information about the character and morphology of the Functionally Graded Materials. This paper presents the results of experiments on joining copper and nickel by using gradient interlayer. Three subsequent layers have been applied on the copper substrate using the brush-plating method: copper, copper and nickel (50wt.% Cu and 50wt.% Ni) and nickel. The Giant Dragon Technical Development Corporation electrolytes have been used in this process. The samples were diffusion bonded with a sample of pure nickel (process parameters: temperature: 860°C, vacuum: 1·10⁻⁵ Tr, time: 30, 120, 360 min.). The morphology and the nature of the gradient interlayer between copper and nickel were examined by analysing the distribution of elements, using SEM, and also gradient interlayer microhardness was examined. The authors state that the character and morphology of the gradient interlayer depends on the conditions of the diffusion bonding process.

KEYWORDS: Functionally Graded Materials, Interlayer, Brush-Plating, Diffusion Bonding

INTRODUCTION

Functionally Graded Materials (FGMs) are such materials, which change their functionality property of at least one of their dimensions – Fig. 1. This may be the gradient of the chemical composition, phase composition, crystalline structure, grain size, etc. – Fig. 2.

Fig. 1: Model of a unidirectional fibre composite with a gradual structure [1]

Fig. 2: Change in: a) the morphology, b) the state, c) crystal structure, d) the distribution pattern [2]

Functionally Graded Materials form a special group of composite materials. They are anisotropic in the macroscopic scale, contrary to conventional composites which, in macroterms, can be considered to be homogeneous.

Fig. 3 shows a schematic representation of classical composite materials in comparison with graded materials, together with the variation of their properties along one dimension. We can see that the properties of the conventional composite do not vary with the material thickness, whereas the FGM changes its properties gradually with depth, which is associated with changes in its microstructure. Thanks to this feature, no sharp discontinuity occurs in, e.g., the distribution of its

thermal expansion coefficient, since the differences in the deformation are “cushioned” and, thus, thermal stresses minimized [3].

Fig. 3: A schematic diagram of the variation of the properties: a) a conventional composite material, b) functionally graded material [3]

Examples of different Functionally Graded Materials are shown in Fig. 4÷7.

Fig. 4: The unidirectional CF/PPS composite with gradual change of local fiber content from top to bottom side [1]

Fig. 5: Thin layered composite with gradually changing TiC-changing (black: Oxidephase, gray: SiC, white: TiC)[4]

Fig. 6: A functionally graded material fabricated by electrophoretic deposition [5]

Fig. 7: Air plasma-sprayed NiCrAlY-PSZ FGM [6]

EXPERIMENTAL WORKS

The study presented in this paper was concerned with the fabrication of graded materials and their applications in joining various materials by the diffusion bonding method. The intermediate layers were deposited by brush-plating (Fig. 8) using electrolytes manufactured by the Giant Dragon Technical Development Corporation [7].

Fig. 8. Brush-plating method [8]

Preliminary experiments were made with copper and nickel – elements that are neighbours in the periodic system and form solid solutions within the whole range of concentrations, but differ in their electrical and thermal properties – Table 1.

The samples were prepared in the following way. Copper, copper + nickel (50wt.% Cu and 50wt.% Ni) and nickel layers were deposited on a copper substrate and then subjected to diffusion bonding with pure nickel – Fig. 9.

It was expected that the diffusion processes proceeding in the material during the diffusion bonding would result in a graded intermediate layer forming between nickel and copper. The results are given in the Tables 2÷5.

Table 1: Selected properties of the copper and nickel [9]

Property	Copper	Nickel
Atomic number	29	28
Atomic mass	63.546	58.6934
Crystalline structure	FCC	FCC
Density [g/cm ³]	8.96	8.90
Melting point [°C]	1083	1453
Boiling point [°C]	2595	2732
linear thermal expansion coefficient within the range from 20 to 100°C [1/K]	$16.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$13.7 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Resistivity w 20°C [$\mu\Omega \cdot m$]	0.0167	0.068
Thermal conductivity at 18°C [W/(cm·K)]	4.0	0.92

Fig.9. The course of the diffusion bonding process

Table 2: Layers deposited by the brush-plating method

Table 3: Ni-FGM-Cu joints (t = 30 min.)

Table 4: Ni-FGM-Cu joints (t = 120 min.)

Table 5: Ni-FGM-Cu joints (t = 360 min.)

CONCLUSIONS

A combination of the two methods: brush-plating and diffusion bonding permits fabricating joints with a functionally graded intermediate layer that shows a mild variation of the microhardness within the region of the joint. The process can be controlled by controlling the diffusion that proceeds within the deposited layers (through easy diffusion paths). The composition and character of the graded layer can be modified by modifying the process duration. The expected results have been confirmed by linear and surface analyses of the Cu and Ni contents in the intermediate layers.

The paper presents preliminary experiments, which are to be continued.

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